

A Study on the Job Satisfaction of Primary School Teachers in Purasaiwakkam Area, Chennai

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ABSTRACT

The education is the primary backbone for the development of any nation in the world. It is a powerful tool which is basis for everything in the society. For provide education to all, the schools and its teacher's plays important role in building the nation. In view of this context, the satisfied teachers in the school can give better education to students rather than dissatisfied teachers. By viewing this as the research focus, this article focuses on the study on the importance of teachers' job satisfaction, It is required to understand the overall teachers' work attitude and work behavior. The paper reviews several factors to ascertain the factors influencing job satisfaction of teacher. The study uses both primary and secondary data. The secondary data were collected various journals and websites. The Primary data were collected by making use of structured questionnaires. The 30 primary school teachers from Helan Sathya Primary School, CSI Primary School and Government Primary School were chosen by convenience sampling method for the study. The questionnaire containing 25 questions with six attributes each. The questionnaire begins with five questions about socio demographic status following with 20 questions with four dimensions namely Career, Colleagues, School and Livelihood. Simple percentage analysis is used to analysis the data. The study finding concludes physical Working Condition, Student interaction, Students IQ, Student Curiosity, Eagerness to learn are some of the concerns of a teacher in teaching. Recognition for Extra Work, clearly defined promotion policies and Salary held a teacher work according to the philosophy/vision/mission/strategy of the management, Teachers works are at times are Challenging & Interesting but on the whole when the management takes of the teachers better, the children are taken care of better. It is suggested that a study can be done among higher secondary school teachers and college teachers.

Keyword-- Job Satisfaction, Primary School Teachers, Chennai

I. INTRODUCTION

The education is the primary backbone for the development of any nation in the world. It is a powerful tool which is basis for everything in the society. For provide education to all, the schools and its teacher's plays

important role in building the nation. In view of this context, the satisfied teachers in the school can give better education to students rather than dissatisfied teachers. The role of teachers in the education as well as in the overall of society can revolutionize, although the vital of their part in both the places was same. Teachers are extremely vital in any educational institution. To catch as well as retain the quality teachers is nowadays a great challenge the school administration. It is important to track their Job satisfaction and check whether he/she is happy with the job they are doing. In education, the primary character of the educator is to have a constructive approach. All instructors must have the probable in addition to comprehensible anticipation to release their responsibility with most excessive commitment to get fulfillment from their work.

Velmurugan, 2016 has pointed out that the organizational development has relay on the job satisfaction of employees. So it is vital to each institution to be on familiar terms with the job satisfaction level of their workers. Job fulfillment is the blend of passionate and mental involvement with any work. Employment Satisfaction is the association sandwiched between what everybody expects in understanding to what all and sundry accomplishes. Several work can't be viably managed without fulfillment. Teachers are significant in structure the country and sprouting natives of the country. Along these lines, work fulfillment is a significant idea that isn't just identified with an individual yet it is important for the general public's well being. Job fulfillment is single aspect that spirit assurance class execution as well as effectiveness of schools. The educators would get stratagem to show their understudies adequately when they are happy with their employments.

Job satisfaction of teachers in the schools is the good number significant factors for achievement rate of educational organizations. So, it is indispensable for each administration to efficiently make use of their teachers. Within an educational institution each teacher is committed. The study attempts to investigate with some of the common variables with newly formed dimensions.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Association and responsibility of educators is simply reliant upon spirit, inspiration and employment satisfaction. In all associations including schools, inspiration and occupation fulfillment assume a significant job. In instructive foundations, educators are the key players who guarantee accomplishment of objectives and destinations of the association and they are key individuals who form the understudies to exceed expectations in their career. An overview was directed on teacher's activity fulfillment in 12 nations about the low work fulfillment of the instructors. It has been recognized that truancy, anomaly and the deficiency of duty are for the most part impacts of low work fulfillment (Bennell & Akyeampong, 2007). Teacher's activity fulfillment isn't just essential to the instructors yet in addition critical to the understudies. Educators maintenance, responsibility can be anticipated by occupation satisfaction (Shann 2001). This demonstrates that activity fulfillment is significant for teachers.

Of the various types of study available about Job Satisfaction, the research will be concentrating on four key areas namely on satisfaction with Career, Colleagues, School and Livelihood (Schwartz, May 2017). For a teacher to concentrate on well on their career support from colleagues are very important. A good support from school both morally and economically will help the teacher build his/her career. This study attempts to find whether any of these dimensions influence Job Satisfaction, The study also attempts to find if there is any an relationships between dimension of job satisfaction.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the job satisfaction level of teachers in the study area.
- To establish the variables influencing job satisfaction of school teachers.
- To provide suggestions to improve the job satisfaction level of teachers in study area.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Herzberg (1987) recommended two types of factors with the intention of contribute to job satisfaction along with job dissatisfaction. The former are the motivators (intrinsic factors): recognition, personal growth, the work itself, opportunities for promotion, achievement. The hygiene factors (extrinsic factors) make certain that employees execute their tasks at minimum level. These are: supervision, security, organization policies, work conditions, salary, relationships with colleagues and supervisors and status are associated with job satisfaction. While the presence of extrinsic factors does not guarantee

job satisfaction, their absence can result in employee job dissatisfaction.

Prakash Khanale and Anil Vaingankar (2006) in their examination viewed that Co-laborers demeanor and workplace impacts work fulfillment of instructors. Singh, Gurmit (2007) in his examination titled distinguish that activity fulfillment of instructor instructors was emphatically identified with their disposition towards educating. Alam (2009) in his investigation finds that huge relationship exists between employment stress and occupation fulfillment. Bhandari, R.A. what's more, Patil, N.H. (2009) in their examination recognizes that activity fulfillment of ladies educators relies upon workplace, work nature and pay.

Singh (2009) in his investigation distinguishes that instructors working in supported schools have abnormal state of fulfillment that educators working in self-financing universities. Thukral and Kaur (2009) in their examination recognize that high dedicated instructors have abnormal state of Job Satisfaction. Marrey (2011) in his investigation establishes that activity fulfillment essentially differs among male and female instructors, experienced and non-experience educators and educators working in Government schools and non-public schools. Singh and Pal (2011) in their investigation see that activity fulfillment fluctuates among urban and country instructors. Nirav Dave and Dr. Dharmesh Raval (2014) in their examination secured that staff position fulfillment is related with Satisfaction from study hall instructing.

Ahmed, Raheem, and Jamal (2003) led an examination on employment fulfillment of 236 instructors in optional school. It was seen that the female instructors are exceptionally fulfilled when contrasted with the male educators. The educators functioning in the Admin School demonstrated higher fulfillment than the educators working in the non-public schools. Gupta and Sahu (2009) directed an investigation on employment satisfaction. It manages the relationship of occupation fulfillment with the hierarchical pressure and spot of control on professional teachers. The results uncovered with the intention of there are no dangerous sexual direction distinction sandwiched between hierarchical stress as well as spot of control on professional teachers.

Noll (2004) analyzed the elements which influence the activity fulfillment of the instructors. It was seen with the intention of the stimulation, instructors association by means of the organization as well as place of work were the variables with the intention of manipulate the activity fulfillment of the educators. Agarwal (2004) had done his examination on employment fulfillment of essential and optional teachers. The outcomes got that the accomplished and wedded educators of government schools are profoundly fulfilled than the instructors of the non-public schools. It likewise uncovered that the age and the conjugal

status have no association with employment fulfillment. R. D. Sharma and Jeevan Jyoti (2006) directed the overview among private and government teachers in Jammu city and the example contains 120 educators. The investigation uncovered the level of fulfillment among the educators isn't high and the non-public school instructors are profoundly fulfilled at the point when contrasted with government educators.

Muchhal and Satish (2010) directed their investigation on occupation fulfillment of elementary teachers in Bagpat region. The investigation uncovers that there exists hugeness among female and male instructors. Iqbar and Akhtar (2012) led their investigation to think about the degree of fulfillment between male and female educators in the government funded school optional instructors utilized in Pakistan and Lahore area. T test can be utilized to look at the satisfaction. The result demonstrated that female educators are fulfilled when contrasted with the male instructors. Raj and Lalitha (2013) directed the review on the degree of employment fulfillment among private and government school teachers. The results demonstrated that there is no noteworthy

distinction in the level of fulfillment of private and government teachers.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Data required for the study is both secondary and primary in nature. Primary data is collected by making use of questionnaires. Secondary data were collected using various journals and websites. The study adopted the convenience sampling method. The sampling was done with 30 primary school teachers in the Purasaiwakkam area. The present study is confined to three primary schools in purasaiwakkam with the help of a research assistant. The schools are Helan Sathya Primary School, CSI Primary School and Government Primary School. The Researcher prepared a questionnaire containing 25 questions with six attributes each. The questionnaire begins with five questions about socio demographic status following with 20 questions with four dimensions. The titles of each dimension are as follows.

Table 1 questionnaire particulars

	Questions	Dimension	Title
	Question a to e	Socio-demographic status	
1	Question No. 1-5	Dimension 1	Job Satisfaction with reference to Career
2	Question No. 6-10	Dimension 2	Job Satisfaction with reference to Colleagues
3	Question No. 11-15	Dimension 4	Job Satisfaction with reference to School
4	Question No. 16-20	Dimension 5	Job Satisfaction with reference to Livelihood

VI. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 2 Socio-Demographic Details

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	7	23.33
Female	23	76.66
Total	30	100
Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-30	5	16.66
31-40	9	30
41-50	8	26.66
51-60	8	26.66
Total	30	100
Total length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-10	5	16.66
11-20	9	30
21-30	8	26.66
31-40	8	26.66
Total	30	100
Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	24	80
Unmarried	6	20

Total	30	100
Children	Frequency	Percentage
1	6	20
2	17	56.66
3 and Above	1	3.33
N A	6	20
Total	30	100

Source: Primary data

Inference

The gender distribution of the respondents consists of (23.33%) of male respondents and (76.66%) of female respondents. The major age groups 20-30(16.66%), 31-40(30%), 41-50(26.66%) and 51-60 (26.66%) followed by 21 to 30. The length of Service of the teachers are 1-10 years of experience (16.66), 11-2- years of experience (30 %), 21-30 years of experience (26.66%) and 31-40 years of experience (26.66%). The marital Status of the teachers are 80% of them are married and 20% of them are unmarried. Regarding no. of Children, Teachers who have one child are 6(20%), teachers who have two children are 17 (56.66). There is one teacher who has three children(3.33%). And teachers who come under the Not Applicable category are 6 (20 %).

The following are the inferences found in each dimensions as follows.

Job Satisfaction with Reference to Career

It was inferred that about 30% of the teachers Strongly Agree and 20 % of the teachers Agree that the teacher is a nation builder. This shows that more than half of them have the feeling that their career is a nation building career. It was inferred that about 26.66 % of the teachers Strongly Agree and 26.66 % of the teachers Agree that teaching is undoubted the best profession. This shows that more than half of the teachers have the feeling that teaching is the best profession. It was inferred that about 33.33 % of the teachers Strongly Agree that the work provides opportunity to display my talent and skill and another 33.33 % Strongly Disagree. This shows that a significant number of respondents disagree that feel that the profession does not provide an opportunity to display their talent and skills. It was inferred that 20% Strongly agree, 20% Disagree and 20% are neutral that they have insecure feeling in the probationary period. It was inferred that 20% Strongly agree, 20% Disagree and 20% are neutral that they would advice their children to adopt teaching profession.

Job Satisfaction with Reference to Colleagues

It was inferred that 30% Strongly agree, 20% Disagree and 20% are neutral in saying that they usually discuss problems/achievements with colleagues. It was inferred that 20% Agree, 40% Strongly agree, 20% are neutral in saying that colleagues are very helpful. It was inferred that 30% Disagree, 26.66 % are neutral and 26.66 % Agree that they sometimes feel that there is none in their

profession in whom they can confide. About 30 % are neutral, 23.33 % agree and 20 % Disagree in saying that Principal usually give sympathetic hearing to any problem brought to his/her notice. I am often given such order by my superiors, which are difficult to carry out.

Job Satisfaction with Reference To School

It is inferred that 20 % Strongly Agree, 43.33% Agree and 13.33 % are neutral in saying that this job allows sufficient time for rest and recreation. It is inferred that 40 % are Neutral, 16.66% Agree and 20 that seniors appreciate their academic knowledge and abilities. It was inferred that 40% are neutral, 16.66 % Agree and 20% Disagree that seniors appreciate my academic knowledge and abilities. It is inferred that 33.33 % are neutral, 23.33% Agree and 23 % Strongly Disagree that they are happy with the academic environment of their School. It is inferred that 33.33 % are neutral, 43.33% Agree and 16.66 % Strongly Agree that the promotions/ appointments in this institution are usually merit-based. It is inferred that 30% Agree 30% are neutral and 20% Strongly Agree that the Heads / Seniors sympathetically listen to my difficulties.

Job Satisfaction with Reference to Livelihood

It is inferred that 46.66 % are neutral, 23.33% Agree and 13.33 % Strongly Agree that the income is sufficient to maintain family according to their status. It was inferred that 43.33 % Agree, 40% Strongly agree that the annual salary increments are released in time by the administrative office. It was inferred that 46.66 % Agree, 23.33 % Strongly agree, 20 % are neutral in saying that they feel their pension is reasonable. It was inferred that 33.33% are neutral 23.33% Strongly agree and 20% Agree that most of the teachers are unable to put their best in their profession because of economic worries. It was inferred that 26.66% Agree, 26.66% Disagree and 23.33% are neutral in saying that they could have earned more had I joined any other profession.

VII. FINDINGS

- It was found that in gender distribution of the respondents consisting (23.33%) of male respondents and (76.66%) of female respondents.

- It was also found that 40% Strongly agree, 20% are neutral in saying that colleagues are very helpful.
- It was found that 40 % are Neutral and 16.66% Agree that seniors appreciate their academic knowledge and abilities.
- It was found that 43.33% Agree and 16.66 % Strongly Agree that the promotions/ appointments in this institution are usually merit-based.
- It was found that 40% strongly agree that the annual salary increments are released in time by the administrative office.

VIII. SUGGESTIONS

- Teacher's satisfaction moreover depends on student's respect. Now-a-days, students on watching films as well as television.
- While the success of teaching depends on teaching the subjects well: the support of colleagues and superiors play a vital role in the career of the teacher.
- Leisure activities are essential for Teachers. Teachers need to spend time with children at home or any other leisure activities.
- Training and Development for Teachers can help teachers so well in their career.
- Encouragement given by senior teachers during probationary period can help junior teachers gain confidence.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

For every teacher Satisfaction in Career and Work place are important for their growth. Working Condition, Student contact, Students IQ, learner Curiosity, Eagerness to study are some of the concerns of a teacher in teaching. Recognition for Extra Work, clearly defined promotion policies and Salary held a teacher work according to the philosophy/vision/mission/strategy of the management,

Teachers works are at times are Challenging & Interesting but on the whole when the management takes of the teachers better, the children are taken care of better.

SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

It is suggested that a study can be done among higher secondary school teachers and college teachers.

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